

Status of Secondary Sector in Nabarangpur, Odisha

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INTRODUCTION

Industry, group of productive enterprises or organizations that produce or supply goods, services, or sources of income. In economics, industries are generally classified as primary, secondary, tertiary, and quaternary; secondary industries are further classified as heavy and light. Primary sector of a nation's economy includes agriculture, forestry, fishing, mining, quarrying, and the extraction of minerals. It may be divided into two categories: genetic industry, including the production of raw materials that may be increased by human intervention in the production process; and extractive industry, including the production of exhaustible raw materials that cannot be augmented through cultivation. The genetic industries include agriculture, forestry and livestock management and fishing—all of which are subject to scientific and technological improvement of renewable resources. The extractive industries include the mining of mineral ores, the quarrying of stone, and the extraction of mineral fuels. Primary industry tends to dominate the economies of undeveloped and developing nations, but as secondary and tertiary industries are developed, its share of the economic output tends to decrease. Secondary industry may be divided into heavy, or large-scale, and light, or small-scale, industry. Large-scale industry generally requires heavy capital investment in plants and machinery, serves a large and diverse market including other manufacturing industries, has a complex industrial organization and frequently a skilled specialized labour force, and generates a large volume of output. Examples would include petroleum refining, steel and iron manufacturing (*see* metalwork), motor vehicle and heavy machinery manufacture, cement production, nonferrous metal refining, meat-packing, and hydroelectric power generation. Tertiary industry sector includes, among others, banking, finance,

insurance, investment, and real estate services; wholesale, retail, and resale trade; transportation; professional, consulting, legal, and personal services; tourism, hotels, restaurants, and entertainment; repair and maintenance services; and health, social welfare, administrative, police, security, and defense services. An extension of tertiary industry that is often recognized as its own sector, quaternary industry, is concerned with information-based or knowledge-oriented products and services. Like the tertiary sector, it comprises a mixture of private and government endeavours. Industries and activities in this sector include information systems and information technology (IT); research and development, including technological development and scientific research; financial and strategic analysis and consulting; media and communications technologies and services; and education, including teaching and educational technologies and services.

Objectives of the Study:

The following were the objectives of the present study.

1. To study the implementation of various government programmes to increase industrialisation
2. To identify the efficacy of the changing administrative structure for the development of Industry.
3. To investigate into the problems responsible for low industrial development
4. To identify the problems faced by the Entrepreneurs.
5. To suggest measures for the overall development Industrial sector in Nabarangpur.

Methodology

Secondary sources of data will also be analyzed which are available from various government

websites, District General Manager, District Industrial Centre, Nabarangpur and through various reports, article and books available in Libraries. Views of some successful industrialists will also ascertain through informal interviews as primary source of data.

Brief Industrial Profile Nabarangpur District General Characteristics of the District:

Nabarangpur is one of the 30 district of Odisha

The district of Nabarangpur was formed on 2nd October, 1992 after being spun off from the erstwhile Koraput district. The headquarters of the district is at Nabarangpur. The predominant economic activities prevalent in the district are agriculture, horticulture, fisheries, animal husbandry, forests, mining in MSME sector and handicrafts and handloom industries in the KVIC/KVIB sector. There are no large scale industries in the district. The district is predominantly inhabited by tribals like Kandha, Paraja, Soura etc.

Administrative Map of Nabarangpur District

Location & Geographical Area.

The district is located on the Southern part of the state and it extends to the North and West up to Bastar district of Chhattisgarh, in the South up to Koraput district and in the East up to Kalahandi district. The district is located at 81 degree to 82 degree longitude and 19 degree to 20 degree latitude. The geographical area of the district is 5291 sq. kms

Topography

The District falls under East Coast Plains and Hills as per Government of India Agro-Climatic Zonal Planning. The entire district except Dabugam block falls under 'Eastern Ghat High Lands'. Dabugam block falls under 'Western Undulating Lands'. The climate is sub-tropical to temperate. It is characterized by hot and dry summer, cool and humid monsoon and cold and dry winter. Two types of soil are found in the district like Red and Laterite. The soil PH is neutral to alkaline and its salinity is normal. The district is predominantly inhabited by tribals like Kandha, Paraja, Soura etc.

Availability of Minerals

The district has occurrence with some mineral deposits like Iron Ore, Quartz, China Clay and Granite etc. However these are not yet commercially exploited.

Forest

Total forest area is 2462.73 Sq. Km. Forest occupies 46.54% of the total geographical area of the district. The major forest products of the district are Timber, Firewood and Bamboos. Besides, the minor forest produce of the district are tamarind, Siali leaves, Karanja seeds, arrow-root, Kusum seeds & Sal seeds. The Kahua brooms and gendulu gums are collected by tribals and procured by LAMPS, TDCC and Oil Orissa. Forest has economic relevance to the district. However, the forest produce are under constant pressure due to the practice of shifting cultivation amongst tribals and increased demand of timber and firewood by the people. A large number of tribal families earn their livelihood from the forest produce. Forestry and wasteland development is proposed to be given greater thrust in District Planning.

Administrative set up

The district comprises of one Sub-Division i.e. Nabarangpur and ten CD Blocks viz; Nabarangpur, Nandahandi, Tentulikhunti, Papdahandi, Kosagumuda, Dabugaon, Umerkote, Jharigaon, Chandahandi and Raigarh. The revenue administration is managed through network of ten Tahasil offices spread out in the district. The district has 13 Police Stations, three towns and 189 Gram Panchayats having 891 Villages. The detail picture of administrative set-up of the district is given below:

1. District Headquarter	: Nabarangpur
2. No. of Sub-Divisions	1
3. No. of Municipality	2
4. No. of NACs	: -
5. No. of CD Blocks	10
6. No. of Tahasils	10
7. No. of Police Stations	13
8. No. of Assembly Constituencies	4
9. No. of Fire Stations	10
10. No. of GPs	189
11. No. of Villages	891

District at a glance:

Sl. No.	Particular	Year	Unit	Statistics
1.	Geographical features			
(A)	Geographical Data			
	i) Latitude	2019	Degree	19 ⁰ 0' to 20 ⁰ 0' (North)
	ii) Longitude	2019	Degree	81 ⁰ 0' to 82 ⁰ 0' (East)
	iii) Geographical Area	2019	Sq. Kms	5291
(B)	Administrative Units			
	i) Sub divisions	2019	No.	1
	ii) Tehsils	2019	No.	10
	iii) Sub-Tehsils	2019	No.	-
	iv) Patwar Circle	2019	No.	-
	v) Panchayat Samitis(CD Blocks)	2019	No.	10
	vi) No. of Municipalities & Corporation	2019	No.	2
	vii) No. of NACs	2019	No.	-
	viii) Gram Panchayats	2019	No.	189
	ix) Census villages(Both Inhabited & Uninhabited)	2019	No.	891
	x) Assembly Area	2019	No.	4
2.	Population(2011 Census Provisional)			
(A)	Sex-wise			
	i) Male	2011	'000	605
	ii) Female	2011	'000	616
(B)	Rural Population	2011	'000	1133
3.	Agriculture			
	Land utilization			
	i) Permanent Pasture	2018-19	'000 hectare	8
	ii) Culturable Waste	2018-19	'000 hectare	15
	iii) Non Agriculture Land	2018-19	'000 hectre	44
	iv) Barren & Unculturable land	2018-19	'000 hectre	9
	v) Net Area sown	2018-19	'000 hectre	176

4.	Forest			
	(i) Forest	2019	Sqr. K.M.	2462.7252
5.	Livestock & Poultry			
A	Cattle			
	i) Cows (Indigenous & CrossBred)	2012	No	394146
	ii) Buffaloes	2012	No	42316
B	Other livestock			
	i) Goats	2012	No	61184
	ii) Pigs	2012	No	9834
	iii) Dogs & Bitches	2012	No	
	iv) Poultry	2012	No	478800
6.	Railways			
	i) Length of rail line	2014-15	Km	0
7.	Roads			
	(a) National Highway	2018-19	Km	42
	(b) State Highway	2018-19	Km	122.59
	(c) Major District Road	2018-19	Km	63.80
	(d) Other District Road	2018-19	Km	420.95
	(e) Rural road	2018-19	Km	1953.52
	(f) Inter Village Road	2018-19	Km	3822.17
	(g) Intra Village Road	2018-19	Km	2351.57
	(h) Forest Road	2018-19	Km	136.46
8.	Communication			
	(a) Post offices	31.03.2018	Nos.	204
9.	Public Health			
	a. Dist. Hqrs. Hospital		N	1
	b. Beds in hospitals		o N	360
	c. Ayurvedic Hospital		o N	22
	d. Homeopathic hospitals		o N	16
	f. Community health centers		o N	10
	g. Primary health centers (hSub-Div. & Other Hospitals	2018	o N	40
	(k) Mobile Health Unit		o N	2
			o N	11
10.	Banking commercial			
	(a) Commercial Bank Branches	As on 31.03.2019	No	64
	(b) Rural Bank Branches		No	39
	(c) Semi Urban Branches		No	25
11.	Education			
	(a) Primary school	2018-19	No	1210
	(b) Middle schools(UpperPrimary)	2018-19	No	608
	(c) Secondary & senior secondaryschools(Junior Colleges)	2018-19	No	239
	(d) Colleges	2018-19	No	Junior College-34 Degree College-9

Source: District at a Glance, 2020, Directorate of Economics & Statistics, Govt. of Odisha,

Existing Status of Industrial Estates/Areas/Growth Centres in the District of Nabarangpur

Sl. No.	Name of Ind. Estate/Area	Total Land (in Acres)	Land Allotted (in Acres)	Prevailing Land Rate Per Acre (In Rs.)	Total Sheds	Sheds Allotted /used	No of vacant sheds	No of units in operation
1	Bamanii Industrial Estate	81.250	-	5,00,000	-	-	-	-
2	Semla Agro Industrial Area	69.810	3.540	3,00,000	-	-	-	-

Source: IDCO, Bhubaneswar

Industrial Scenario of Nabarangpur District**Industry at a Glance**

Sl. No	Head	Unit	Particulars
1.	REGISTERED MICRO & SMALL UNIT	NOs	5664
3.	REGISTERED MEDIUM & LARGE UNIT	Nos.	3
4.	EMPLOYMENT IN SMALL SCALE INDUSTRIES	Nos.	22556
5.	EMPLOYMENT IN LARGE AND MEDIUM INDUSTRIES	Nos.	238
6.	NO. OF INDUSTRIAL AREA	Nos.	2
7.	INVESTMENT OF SMALL SCALE IND.	IN LACS	25094.51
8.	INVESTMENT OF MEDIUM & LARGE SCALE INDUSTRIES	IN LACS	3911

Source: O/o. Directorate of Industries, Cuttack

Year Wise Trend of Units Registered

YEAR	NUMBER OF REGISTERED UNITS	EMPLOYMENT	INVESTMENT (lakh Rs.)
Upto 1984-85	105	427	38.8
1985-86	20	116	11.49
1986-87	2	5	1.17
1987-88	5	41	5.61
1988-89	1	3	1.71
1989-90	2	13	2.58
1990-91	1	13	3.46
1991-92	6	42	27.28
1992-93	0	0	0
1993-94	48	225	29.06
1994-95	16	59	4.74
1995-96	17	79	10.89
1996-97	12	107	24.53
1997-98	11	64	46.97
1998-99	26	89	21.06
1999-2000	23	184	83.76
2000-01	29	196	18.27
2001-02	31	140	125.54
2002-03	23	130	12.88
2003-04	32	357	61.27
2004-05	35	307	125.17
2005-06	35	175	29.26
2006-07	35	659	140.95
2007-08	28	681	105.73

2008-09	19	235	53.14
2009-10	20	129	39.08
2010-11	20	202	73.35
2011-12	15	309	128.68
2012-13	15	254	95.32
2013-14	82	657	1329.00
2014-15	428	1658	2691.86
2015-16	1146	4023	4074.64
2016-17	1321	4262	6819.08
2017-18	1024	3096	4782.58
2018-19	1031	3619	4075.60
Total	5664	22556	25094.51

Source: Directorate of Industries, Cuttack and District at a Glance, 2020, Directorate of Economics & Statistics, Govt. of Odisha, Bhubaneswar

DETAILS OF EXISTING MICRO & SMALL ENTERPRISES UNITS IN THE DISTRICT by End Of 2016

Sl. No.	TYPE OF INDUSTRY	NUMBER OF UNITS	INVESTMENT (Lakh Rs.)	EMPLOYMENT
1	Food & Allied	488	3880.26	4322
2	Chemical & Allied	8	55.19	53
3	Electrical & Electronics	2	2.3	5
4	Engineering & Metal based	112	342.32	494
5	Forest and Wood based	6	10.65	21
6	Glass and Ceramics	20	315.56	333
7	Live Stock & Leather	1	2.1	3
8	Paper & Paper Product	13	38.14	57
9	Rubber & Plastics	3	3.67	11
10	Textiles	29	361	200
11	Misc. Manufacturing	12	78.3	53
12	Repairing & Servicing	700	2594.32	2231
Total		1394	7683.81	7783

Source: Directorate of Industries, Orissa

Large Scale Industries / Public Sector undertakings (NIL)

Growth Trend

The growth trend of registered units in the district from 1984-85 to 2013-14 is asymmetrical and negligible. However, from 2014-15, there is continuous rise in the No. of registered units increasing significantly to 1321 in 2016-17, 1024 in 2017-18 and 1031 in 2018-19. Since 2013-14 there is a sudden and significant rise in the number of units registered, employment generated and investment incurred. It is because more number of units were gone into production.

Vendorisation / Ancillarisation of the Industry

As there is no large scale industry in the district, there is little scope for ancillary development. However, some ancillary and downstream industries can be promoted basing upon the requirements of the mother plants located in the neighbouring districts. In this liberalized era, the place or locality is not a rigid criteria for development of ancillary industries. This can be done taking into view the requirement and demand of the mother plants located inside the state. Similarly, as a number of large scale industries are on the pipeline specially on steel, mine and power sector for which MOU has already been signed. So, there is scope for ancillarization in near future.

Medium Scale Enterprises

Sl. No	Name and address of the unit	Investment (Rs. in lakh)	Employment	Item of production
1.	M/s Mangalam Timbers, Nabarangpur	3210	196	Medium Density Fibre Board
2	M/s. Glaze hotel and resorts pvt Ltd.	500	40	Services
3	M/s. Swaraj Services	201	2	Services
Total		3911	238	

Source: Directorate of Industries, Cuttack, DIC, Nabarangpur and UAM Portal of O/o DC (MSMS), New Delhi

Service Enterprises

There is positive growth with respect to service enterprises like transport, and repairing services. There is also services activities like grinding of Food grain like rice milling etc.

Potentials Areas for Service Industry

Activities under service and business sectors generally require less capital and labour intensive in nature. It is widely feasible because of growing need towards these services. The following servicing units are identified for the districts.

1. Cycle/Rickshaw Repairing unit
2. Agro servicing centres
3. Retreading of tyre
4. Two wheeler and Four wheeler repairing
5. Electrical repairing shop and motor winding
6. Beauty parlor
7. Colour Laboratory
8. Dry Cleaning
9. Restaurant /Hotel
10. Mobile Repairing /Servicing
11. Packaged Tourism Centre
12. Industrial Consultancy
13. Cold storage/Rural Godown
14. Grain Milling

Potential for new MSMEs

Taking into the consideration on availability of raw material and local demand, the following resource based demand based MSMEs are suggested.

1. Rice Mill
2. Cashew nut processing
3. Mushroom processing
4. Maize based products
5. Leaf cup and plates
6. Tamarind Powder/kernel/paste
7. Dal Mill
8. Spices Grinding
9. Cattle/Poultry Feed
10. Readymade Garment
11. Cement products /Hollow Bricks
12. Dairy /Milk Products
12. Stone Crusher
13. Rice Bran Oil
14. Decorative Wood Craft
15. Marble/Granite Cutting and Polishing
16. Lac gum and Lac Toys
17. Malted Corn flakes
18. Coal Briquets
19. Mechanised Bakery
20. Papad Manufacturing

21. Arrowroot Powder
22. Bee Keeping and Honey processing
23. Packaged Drinking water
24. Aluminium utensil
25. Voltage Stabiliser
26. Powerloom

Existing Clusters of Micro & Small Enterprise

Detail Of Major Clusters

Sl No	Name of the Cluster (Product)	Location	District	No.of MSMEs In the Cluster (approx.)
1	Maize processing Cluster	Umerkote	Nabarangpur	40 nos.
2	LAC processing Cluster	Chandahandi	Nabarangpur	30 nos.
3	Cashew Cluster	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	20 nos.
4	Rice mill Cluster		Nabarangpur	30 nos.
5	Tribal Jewellery Cluster	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	150 nos.
6	Horn Processing Cluster	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	25 nos.
7	Pottery Cluster	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	30 nos.
8	Agricluture implements Cluster	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	25 nos.
9	Fishery Cluster	Paphadahan di	Nabarangpur	25 nos.
10	Handicrafts (Terracota)	Nabarangpur	Nabarangpur	120 nos.

MSMEs registered in the Udyog Aadhaar

Sl. No.	District Name	Udyog Aadhaar Regd.	Micro	Small	Medium
1	Nabarangapur	648	551	95	2

Source: UAM Portal, O/o DC (MSME), New Delhi

General Issues Raised By Industry Association

1. There are potentialities for resource based enterprises. But the peoples lack entrepreneurship and they do not have interest on value addition for which wider sensitization and awareness are required.
2. Frequent disruption of Power
3. Finance/Credit –Most of the entrepreneurs and also Bankers at Branch level have no idea on FINANCE LINKED SHEME like CGTMSE, CLCSS etc.
4. Lack of marketing facilities due to inaccessibility to most of the areas for which there need improvement in infrastructure and transportation.
5. No railway line exists in the district.

Prospects of training programmes during 2020-21

Sl. No.	Name of the programme	Subject	No of proposed programme to be conducted
1	ESDP	1. Mobile phone repairing 2. Electronics items 3. Food Processing 4. Household Chemicals	1
2	MDP	1. Computer office Management 2. Leadership & Personality Skill Development	1
3	EAP	-	2
4	IMC	-	5

Action plan for MSME Schemes during 2020-21.

S. No.	Name of the Scheme	Proposed activity on the scheme
1.	MSE-CDP	01 no. of awareness programme will beorganised.
2.	Export Awareness Programme	01 no. of awareness programme will beorganised.
3.	PMS	Handholding Support will be provided
4.	International cooperation	Handholding Support will be provided
5.	VDP	10 nos. of units will be motivated underthe scheme
6.	CLCS-TU	Handholding Support will be provided
I.	Lean Manufacturing	01 cluster will be identified
II.	Design Clinic	01 seminar will be organized.
III.	IPR	01 seminar will be organized.
IV.	ICT-Digital MSME	05 Units will be motivated for the registration in digital MSME website
V.	ZED	01 seminar would be organized
VI.	Business Incubator scheme	01 seminar would be organized
VII.	CLCS	01 seminar would be organized

NB: These have been proposed and would be conducted subject to availabilityof sanction

STEPS TO SET UP MSMEs

Following are the brief description of different agencies for rendering assistanceto the entrepreneurs.

Sl. No.	Type of assistance	Name, address and website of agencies
1.	Provisional Registration Certificate – Udyog Aadhaar Memorandum(UAM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Directorate of Industries, Govt. of Odisha, KilaMaidan , Cuttack, www.as.ori.nic.in/diorissa/ General Manager, DIC, Nawarangpur. www.udyogaadhaar.gov.in/
2.	Identification ofproject profiles, techno-economic andmanagerial consultancy services,market survey and economic survey reports	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MSME Development Institute, Vikash Sadan, College Square, Cuttack www.msmedicuttack.gov.in
3.	Land and Industrial shed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MD, IDCO, IPICOL House, Janpath, Bhubaneswar www.idco.in
4.	Financial assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MD, OSFC, OMP Square, Cuttack, www.osfcindia.com MD, IPICOL, Janpath, Bhubaneswar, www.ipicolorissa.com Director, KVIC, 6, Budha Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.kvic.org.in Secretary, KVIB, Near Rupali Square,Bhubaneswar General Manager, NABARD, Nayapalli, Bhubaneswar, https://www.nabard.org/english/Orissa.aspx General Manager, SIDBI, OCHC Building, Unit-3,Bhubaneswar, www.sidbi.com Nationalized Banks
5.	For raw materials under Govt. supply	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> M.D, OSIC, Khapuria Industrial Estate, Cuttack,www.osicltd.in
6.	Plant and machinery under hire/purchasebasis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional Manager, NSIC, Abdul Hamid Street, Kolkata Sr. Branch Manager, NSIC, Link Road, Cuttack, www.nsic.co.in
7.	Power/Electricity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chairman, GRID Corporation of Odisha, GRIDCO, Saheed Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.gridco.co.in Chairman, CESCO, IDCO Tower, Bhubaneswar, www.cescoorissa.com

8.	Technical Know-how	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Director, MSME Development Institute, Vikash Sadan, College Square, Cuttack- 753003, www.msmedicuttack.gov.in
9.	Quality & standard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bureau of Indian Standards(BIS), Ministry of Civil Supplies, Consumer Affairs & Public Distributors, Govt. of India, 62/63, Ganganagar, Bhubaneswar, www.bis.org.in/dir/bhbo.htm • Director National Productivity Council, Ministry of Industry, Govt. of India, A/7, Surya Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.npcindia.gov.in/offices • Director, MSME Development Institute, Vikash Sadan, College Square, Cuttack-753003
10.	Marketing/Export assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Director, MSME Development Institute, Vikash Sadan, College Square, Cuttack - 753003 • Export Credit Guarantee Corporation of India Ltd., A-77, Saheed Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.ecgc.in/portal/servicenetwork/easternpopup.asp • Director, EPM, Ashoka Market, Master Canteen, Bhubaneswar, www.depmodisha.nic.in • Sr.Branch Manager, NSIC, Link Road, Cuttack.
11.	Other Promotional Agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MD, APICOL, Near Baramunda Bus Stand, Bhubaneswar, www.apicol.co.in • Director, Horticulture, Udyan Bhavan, Nayapalli, Bhubaneswar, www.orihort.in • Director, Animal Husbandry & Veterinary Services, Mangalabag, Cuttack, www.odishaahvs.com • Director, Handicraft & Cottage Industries, Saheed Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.dhorissa.ori.nic.in • Director of Textiles, Satya Nagar, Bhubaneswar, www.odisha.gov.in/textiles • Director of Fisheries, Jobra, Cuttack, http://www.odishafisheries.com • Coconut Development Board, Nayapalli, Bhubaneswar, www.coconutboard.nic.in/odishacday.htm • Coir Board, Jagamara, Bhubaneswar, www.coirboard.gov.in • Principal Chief Conservator of Forest, Aranya Bhavan, Chandrasekharpur, Bhubaneswar, www.odishaforest.in

Conclusion

Industry is an important economic activity of human mankind. Industry is related with processing of raw material, production of goods which are used by consumers. Industry is a systematic activity which manufactures goods to satisfy human wants and organize by employee and employers. Industrialization transforms human group from an agrarian society into an industrial society. Industrialization is a part of social and economic change where economic development through

modernization has takes place. The inefficient public sector has lead to corruption and therefore lowered the quality of production and industrialization. There is also a lack of skilled of labour which has slowed down the process of industrialization Research in industrial development and industrial investment in India has been increasing day by day. But justification with the word Anti-Regionalism and balanced industrial development is the need of the hour.